

Assessing Yield Disparities: Anticipated versus Optimal Rooftop Photovoltaic Systems and Implications for Prosumer Viability

Dominik Keiner,* Dmitrii Bogdanov, Stefan Krauter, and Christian Breyer*

Solar photovoltaics, especially rooftop systems also called distributed solar photovoltaics, are crucial in the ongoing energy transition. Modeling these systems is vital to understanding their role in a decentralized energy system. While ground-mounted photovoltaic power plants are easier to model, generalizing yield profiles for rooftop systems is challenging. This study aims to estimate yield loss effects for rooftop solar photovoltaic systems compared to optimized ground-mounted systems. Anticipated yield losses are 18% for residential, 7% for commercial, and 4% for industrial rooftop systems. The impact on residential prosumers' viability is assessed by comparing prosumer system optimization results with and without yield losses. Results show a non-uniform change in installed solar photovoltaic and battery capacities, with a tendency to compensate for reduced yields by increasing photovoltaic capacity by up to 20%, given favorable cost prospects by 2050. The annualized total cost of energy for prosumer households could therefore increase by up to 20% by 2050. Despite yield reductions, installing a solar photovoltaic prosumer system remains more favorable than relying entirely on-grid electricity. This study highlights the importance of considering yield losses in rooftop solar photovoltaics and the significant role of prosumers despite identified yield losses.

in the ongoing energy transition.^[2] The global potential for electricity generation from rooftop solar PV alone can be estimated to about 27 000 TWh.^[3] This importance is accentuated by ongoing solar PV installations. In 2022, distributed solar PV installations in the top 10 markets were 89.9 GW_p, which is 38.1% of the total installed solar PV capacity that year.^[4] Energy system transition research indicates the important role of solar PV prosumers in the future. For example, the global results of Bogdanov et al.^[5] estimate more than 15% of the global installed solar PV capacity to be assigned to solar PV prosumers by 2050. Jacobson et al.^[6] found a share of solar PV prosumers in total installed PV capacities of about 39% in 2050, however, for a lower total installed solar PV capacity as in Bogdanov et al.^[5] Higher installations shares nowadays compared to partly lower shares estimated for the future underline the important role of rooftop solar PV for the early phases of the global energy transition. As a fact, while rooftop solar PV

dominated the global solar PV market in the 1990s and 2000s,^[4] the share of rooftop solar PV has stayed more or less constant at around 50% since the renewable energy installations see a strong uptake.^[7] Rooftop solar PV prosumerism,^[8] that is, the use of rooftop solar PV electricity within the household for covering power demand, heat demand, charging the electric vehicle, as well feeding electricity to the grid, has been shown to be beneficial worldwide.^[9,10] Prosumers are of high importance for the overall energy transition.^[11] Research suggests that distributed renewable energy and prosumerism might help to support the energy transition in societies.^[12,13]

There are numerous studies available assessing the performance and expected yield of rooftop PV systems for different sites, countries, or regions globally. Only very few studies cover a comparative analysis of ground-mounted versus rooftop solar PV power plants. Awan et al.^[14] compared the performance of ground-mounted versus rooftop solar PV for different row spacing in a hot environment. In their approach, the energy saved for cooling of the building is added to the electricity yield of the rooftop PV system, leading to a better performance of the rooftop PV system compared to the ground-mounted counterpart for the overall energy balance. Bansal et al.^[15] reviewed the different performances of fixed and single-axis tracking solar PV power

1. Introduction

Solar photovoltaics (PV) has been crowned as the “new king” by the International Energy Agency (IEA).^[1] Distributed energy sources such as rooftop solar PV are expected to be a major pillar

D. Keiner, D. Bogdanov, C. Breyer
School of Energy Systems
LUT University
Yliopistonkatu 34, 53850 Lappeenranta, Finland
E-mail: dominik.keiner@lut.fi; christian.breyer@lut.fi

S. Krauter
Faculty of Computer Science, Electrical Engineering and Mathematics,
Electrical Energy Technology-Sustainable Energy Concepts (EET-NEK)
Paderborn University
Warburger Str. 100, 33098 Paderborn, Germany

 The ORCID identification number(s) for the author(s) of this article can be found under <https://doi.org/10.1002/solr.202400435>.

© 2024 The Author(s). Solar RRL published by Wiley-VCH GmbH. This is an open access article under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License, which permits use, distribution and reproduction in any medium, provided the original work is properly cited.

DOI: 10.1002/solr.202400435

plants, while except for degradation, the assessment is made without differentiation of ground-mounted and rooftop solar PV, leaving out major differences in these two system options. Apart from these rare examples, no study could be identified covering a dedicated overview on the yield differences between the optimal and anticipated yield of rooftop solar PV plants versus ground-mounted utility-scale solar PV power plants.

In order to show pathways for the global energy transition, energy system transition modeling is an important research area. However, a dedicated modeling of solar PV prosumers is included only in a few models, and if included, often insufficiently implemented. In the most used energy system model for highly renewable energy systems^[16] EnergyPLAN,^[17] solar PV resources are aggregated into one technology option, requiring additional efforts for a differentiated modeling of various PV options, such as utility-scale and rooftop solar PV. Some versions of the TIMES model,^[18] explicitly JRC-EU-TIMES^[19] differentiate utility-scale, high concentration, and rooftop solar PV. The GENeSYS-MOD or OSeMOSYS model^[20,21] also differentiate the utility-scale, and rooftop solar PV.^[22] However, TIMES and GENeSYS-MOD/OSeMOSYS models use the time slices approach instead of full hourly resolution, which may affect the system optimization, especially short- and long-term energy storage in the case of high shares of RE. Only the GATOR-GCMOM/LOADMATCH^[23] and LUT-ESTM^[5] tools explicitly differentiate prosumers PV and optimize the system in full hourly resolution. Neumann et al.^[24] include rooftop solar PV in addition to utility-scale solar PV by assuming 16% of the total PV capacity without individual rooftop solar PV optimization or further detailing on the share as part of the PyPSA framework, whereas an improved method with distributed PV modeling is available for PyPSA.^[25] Some studies use rooftop solar PV; however, they do not provide minimum information on what basis it is considered in their energy system modeling,^[26,27] or consider rooftop PV potential while not disclosing whether it was considered in the modeling.^[28] Others do not provide information whether rooftop and utility-scale solar PV is differentiated at all.^[29–32] This overview on major energy system modeling teams and models used indicate substantial gaps in proper inclusion of rooftop solar PV in the analyses, as some even ignore rooftop solar PV at all, and differentiated information on the rooftop solar PV segments and their yield modeling are largely missing across all major models and teams.

The photovoltaic power systems programmed of the IEA (IEA-PVPS) Task 13 “Reliability and Performance of Photovoltaic Systems” provides a set of reports assessing performance issues of solar PV, including uncertainty in yield assessments^[33,34] and performance assessment of new solar PV systems.^[35] A dedicated study on different yield loss effects to assess the yield disparity for rooftop PV systems in comparison to ground-mounted systems on global scale is not yet available. Furthermore, an assessment of the impact of the reduced yield on the techno-economic performance of solar PV prosumer systems is not yet available. This study aims to close these research gaps. The novelties of this study comprise: 1) Global-local rooftop PV yield disparity assessment of the anticipated rooftop PV yield in comparison to the optimal yield of ground-mounted utility-scale solar PV power plants. 2) Assessment of the system impact of cost-optimized residential solar PV prosumer systems

applying the optimal yield and anticipated yield to point out the importance of detailed consideration of solar PV prosumers in energy system transition modeling.

This study aims to contribute new knowledge to the energy system modeling research to correctly assess the role of solar PV prosumers in detailed energy system transition research. The identified values for yield losses of rooftop solar PV systems versus easier to model ground-mounted solar PV systems aims to improve the consideration of rooftop solar PV in future energy system models with high spatial resolution and extent, which do not yet consider dedicated rooftop solar PV resources.

2. Methods and Data

2.1. Loss Effects in Rooftop Solar Photovoltaic Systems

There are several loss effects identified for residential solar PV rooftop systems. As structured in this sub-section, they can be assigned to an environmental, cell and module, and system level. The sub-section also provides information on the adaption of residential yield losses to commercial and industrial system sizes. The losses are compared on a normalized level to available data from Killinger et al.^[36] Therefore, the choice of values mentioned in the following sub-sections is done having the target value in mind. The comparison of total yield losses based on these values and the yield results by Killinger et al.^[36] however, is presented in the Section 4.1. This study is carried out assuming that losses from curtailment are not yet significantly important for rooftop solar PV systems.

2.1.1. Environmental Level

This level consists of the orientation of the modules, so nonoptimal tilt or azimuth of the solar PV modules, and shading by houses, structures, vegetation, urban obstacles, etc. Therefore, the environmental level includes causes of yield reduction based on the reduced irradiance on the modules.

The effect of nonoptimal orientation is estimated based on irradiance data for several sites around the world. **Table 1** lists all studies included in the estimation of nonoptimal orientation impact.

The polar contour plots for the tilt angle and azimuth provided in the studies allow for the estimation of a worst-case effect of

Table 1. Studies included for estimating the nonoptimal module orientation based on polar contour plots provided.

Study	Year	Location
Rowlands et al. ^[74]	2011	Ontaria, Canada
Byrd ^[75]	2012	Auckland, New Zealand
Khoo et al. ^[76]	2014	Singapore
Hartner et al. ^[77]	2015	Vienna, Austria
Matthiss et al. ^[78]	2015	Widderstall, Germany
Kichou et al. ^[79]	2019	Prague, Czechia
Oh and Park ^[80]	2019	Seoul, South Korea
Yu et al. ^[81]	2019	Tokyo, Japan

≈5% yield reduction. The worst-case would be an orientation toward East or West instead of facing the equator. A typical rooftop tilt angle of ≈25°–40° is presumed. As rooftop PV modules face on average different directions, however, with a tendency toward the equator, an average effect of 2% for nonoptimal module orientation is chosen.

Yield losses by obstacles, structures, vegetation, etc. are always case-specific for each rooftop PV system, and are therefore challenging to estimate on a general basis. Another problem is that such effects are rarely reported in literature. Killinger et al.^[36] estimate ≈7.4% irradiation losses in Uppsala, Sweden. Trzmiel et al.^[37] report ≈7.5–11% irradiation losses for a residential house in Poland. Berardi and Graham^[38] estimate up to 30% losses in a worst-case scenario for the case of Toronto, Canada. For this study, an effect of 7.5% is chosen for residential solar PV irradiation loss due to obstacles. This loss only includes shading that reduces the irradiation on the modules but still providing enough irradiation for the modules to work. Shading that activates the bypass diodes of the module is assigned to the system level in Section 2.1.3.

2.1.2. Cell and Module Level

The cell and module level refers to the physics of the solar PV module. The only effect that is different from a utility-scale power plant is the reduced ventilation of the modules, since they are usually mounted directly to the rooftop. Again, such effects are rarely studied for rooftop systems. For non-ventilated façade systems in Stockholm, Sweden, London, Great Britain, and Madrid, Spain, Yun et al.^[39] estimated ≈2.5% yield reduction due to higher cell temperatures. A nonventilated rooftop system studied by Ritzen et al.^[40] in the Netherlands showed ≈2.6% yield reduction related to the module temperatures. The impacts of a green roof versus concrete and the impact of wind versus no wind for mounted modules on a rooftop in Bucaramanga, Colombia was tested to be 2–3% ± 0.4% by Osuma-Pinto and Ordóñez-Plata.^[41] Therefore, a global average of 2.5% yield losses due to less sufficient module cooling on rooftops is chosen.

2.1.3. System Level

On the system level, the inverter performance plays a main role. One loss factor might be the insufficient maximum power point tracking of inverters if modules are partially shaded. Bründlinger et al.^[42] found this effect to reduce the yield by ≈2%. Another issue is the inverter sizing. According to Kouro et al.^[43] bigger inverters show higher efficiencies than smaller ones, but this effect is rather small with 1% yield loss. The biggest contribution at this level, however, is the fact that smaller PV systems consist of only a few strings. In the case that only one module is shaded in such a way, that the full module is not operable, the whole module string is not able to work accordingly. This effect can only be estimated indirectly, that is, by equipping each module with its own microinverter. No evidence could be found for a large penetration of microinverters, also called module inverters, for the foreseeable future. The studies done by Dong et al.^[44] and Mohd^[45] allow for a yield reduction of 5–10%. In this study, an average value of 7.5% is chosen.

2.1.4. Adaption for Commercial and Industrial Rooftop Systems

Solar PV prosumers cover residential houses as well as commercial buildings (retailers, stores, supermarkets, etc.) and industrial buildings (big manufacturing buildings, large logistic buildings). The loss effects obtained for residential systems must therefore be adapted to different applications. Unfortunately, due to the lack of data allowing for a comparison of ground-mounted solar PV simulation data to rooftop solar PV yield data as done for residential systems, this must be done via an educated guess.

The nonoptimal orientation will in some cases be significantly improved, for example, on flat roofs with mounting structures. Therefore, this impact is assumed to be improved to 1% yield loss for both commercial and industrial systems. Reduction in irradiance from obstacles or vegetation, however, can be presumed to have a much less impact for commercial and industrial systems than for residential rooftops, since these systems are more situated in industrial areas, or in areas with more spacing between buildings (e.g., for parking lots or similar). Furthermore, obstacles on the roofs such as chimneys are not as much a problem than for residential rooftop systems. This effect is chosen to contribute 2% yield loss for commercial systems and 1% yield loss for industrial systems.

Insignificant ventilation still plays a role, especially for commercial systems, as many of these systems might not be installed on flat roofs with a mounting structure, but on the rooftop itself. Industrial systems can be presumed to be mostly flat roofs requiring a mounting structure, which improves ventilation of the solar PV modules. For commercial systems, this effect is only slightly reduced to 2% compared to residential systems. For industrial systems a contribution of 1% is assumed to account for higher temperatures due to rooftop material other than bare ground.

One major issue of only a few strings in the system will be significantly improved for both commercial and industrial systems due to the bigger capacities installed, allowing for, and requiring more strings. Nevertheless, this effect will not completely vanish. Therefore, a 2% yield reduction effect for commercial systems and 1% for industrial systems is considered.

2.2. Other Loss Effects

Other causes for yield losses that impact rooftop solar PV systems equally as ground-mounted systems and, therefore, do not cause an additional yield loss, are not included in this assessment. Such loss affects are, for example, losses due to soiling of the modules. The self-cleaning of the modules via precipitation^[46,47] is assumed to be equal for fixed-tilted, ground-mounted solar PV power plants and rooftop systems. For other accumulation of dirt on the modules, such as bird droppings,^[48] no evidence could be found in literature that rooftop solar PV systems would be more affected than ground-mounted systems. Air pollution^[49] and humidity or fog^[50] could be factors for lower rooftop solar PV systems, since rooftop systems are on average located in metropolitan regions, which are commonly located near the coast, in contrast to utility-scale solar PV power plants. However, compared to the total rooftop PV installations of a country or region, these effects might be negligible for

aggregated energy systems. Additionally, yield disparities due to different degradation effects of rooftop solar PV systems compared to ground-mounted systems are not covered in this study. Degradation effects are investigated in ongoing research and reports as of the IEA-PVPS Task 13 were able to present insights^[51] as well as academic research such as from Jordan et al.^[52] Herceg et al.^[53] and Kaaya et al.^[54]

2.3. Solar Photovoltaic Yield and Prosumer Modeling

The calculation of the full load hours (FLH) per region is based on a global 400×800 nodes gridded data ($0.45^\circ \times 0.45^\circ$) in full hourly resolution and then aggregated with the method presented by Bogdanov and Breyer.^[55] For the calculation of yield profiles, an optimization of tilt angles for ground-mounted solar PV power plants is done based on Breyer and Schmidt.^[56] The basis of the yield modeling is hourly global gridded data by NASA for the year 2005,^[57,58] reprocessed by the German Aerospace Center.^[59]

Optimal ground-mounted solar PV power plants refer to optimally tilted systems as used by Afanasyeva et al.^[60] for comparison of single-axis tracking solar PV power plants to optimally fixed-tilted solar PV power plants. The optimal tilt angles of ground-mounted solar PV power plants have been calculated based on an optimization of leveled cost of electricity (LCOE) on high spatial resolution globally as done by Breyer and Schmidt.^[56] Instead of using a rule-of-thumb for tilt angle optimization, the optimal tilt angle has been found in these studies by calculating the irradiation on the titled surface of the PV modules using the aforementioned resource data for different tilt angles and subsequently calculating the LCOE for each tilt angle. The optimal tilt angle in terms of lowest LCOE might differ from

the tilt angle with the highest global irradiation, as stated by Breyer and Schmidt.^[56]

Residential solar PV prosumers are modeled using the LUT-PROSUME linear optimization model according to Keiner et al.^[10] The model structure with all its components is shown in **Figure 1**.

The modeling details of the prosumer system are described by Keiner et al.^[10] including all techno-economic parameters and demand numbers. Equally, the simulation is done for 145 regions as depicted in **Figure 2**. The regions are clustered in nine major regions to simplify the classification of results and discussion. Figure 2 also shows the FLH of optimal solar PV systems, which means optimally tilted ground-mounted solar PV power plants as used by Bogdanov et al.^[5]

To study the impact of reduced yield on solar PV prosumers, the scenario including a grid connection and a standard car (ON-STDC, cf. Keiner et al.^[10]) is chosen for this study representing the most common system structure for residential solar PV prosumers. The impact analysis is done by comparing the installed rooftop PV capacity per average residential home, the installed stationary battery capacity per average residential home, and the annualized total cost of energy (ATCE). The ATCE include the annualized cost for component investment (capital expenditure), operational expenditure, and electricity drawn from the grid (cf. Keiner et al.^[10]).

3. Results

3.1. Optimal versus Anticipated Yield

In a recent study, Killinger et al.^[36] provided detailed yield data for rooftop PV systems from all over the globe. **Table 2** shows the

Figure 1. Solar PV prosumer model structure including technology components and energy flows. STD-C, standard car (battery electric vehicle); V2H-C, car with vehicle-to-home option (to be used as an electricity storage); WEL, water electrolyzer; HCP, hydrogen compressor; HES, hydrogen energy storage; FC, fuel cell; PtH, power-to-heat (heat pump or heating cartridge); TES, thermal energy storage.

Figure 2. Geographic overview on the 145 regions for simulations, clustered in nine major regions (top) and solar PV yield in optimal conditions for ground-mounted power plants (bottom). MENA, Middle East and North Africa; SSA, sub-Saharan Africa; SAARC, South Asian Association for Regional Cooperation.

mean yield per installed capacity for the different countries compared to the optimal ground-mounted yield according to Bogdanov et al.^[5]

The comparison underlines the claim that yield disparities are always location dependent. However, it can also be seen that most of the regions show a yield deviation of at least 10%, except the UK and Japan. Almost two thirds of the regions show a yield deviation of at least 15%. Denmark shows the highest deviation of 31%. To estimate a global average value, the average is taken weighted by the number of systems, leading to 18% yield disparity of residential rooftop PV systems (rooftop PV systems ≤ 25 kW_p).

Figure 3 shows the total anticipated rooftop PV yield versus the optimal yield of ground-mounted solar PV power plants.

The yield loss effects chosen for the environmental, cell and module, and system level based on available literature in Section 3.2 are in line with the estimated global average value of 18%. The reduction of the loss effects for commercial systems lead to a total discrepancy of 7% compared to optimal ground-mounted systems. Industrial rooftop systems show the smallest yield discrepancy with a total of 4%. The yield differences of residential, commercial, and industrial rooftop solar PV systems can be seen in **Figure 4**, if the aforementioned

Table 2. Comparison of Killinger et al.^[36] yield numbers for rooftop solar PV systems ≤ 25 kWp to the optimally tilted, fixed ground-mounted yield number as used in the LUT modeling (Bogdanov et al.^[5]).

Region	Killinger et al. rooftop [kWh/kW _p]	Number of systems	LUT optimally tilted fixed, ground-mounted [kWh/kW _p]	Deviation [%]
Austria	1043	1000	1207	14
Belgium	922	15 000	1030	10
Denmark	784	2100	1131	31
France	1101	23 300	1317	16
Germany	862	5 885 000	1053	18
Italy	1143	5400	1455	21
Japan	1221	10 800	1340.5	9
Netherlands	853	6200	1030	17
UK	897	28 700	956	6
United States North	1014	11 900	1317	23
United States South	1432	73 100	1686.5	15
System-weighted average	–	–	–	18

Figure 3. Total anticipated annual yield loss for residential, commercial, and industrial rooftop solar PV systems. Orientation and shading refer to the losses on environmental level, ventilation is the main reason for losses on cell and module level, and the inverter and string configuration represents the system level.

yield discrepancy factors are applied to the optimal ground-mounted yield as shown previously in Figure 3.

The relative yield difference applied to different regions globally naturally leads to different total losses. Regions with high FLH predominantly in the sunbelt may lose 250–360 FLH compared to ground-mounted systems, while the absolute losses in the Nordics may not exceed 150–200 FLH. The yield of rooftop PV systems in the sunbelt with 18% yield reduction, however, still exceeds the optimal yield of the Nordic regions (cf. Figure 2). The sunbelt regions still show a yield of ≈ 1200 –1800 FLH whereas optimal ground-mounted systems in the Nordics have yields of typically up to 1200 FLH. Numeric results for the optimal and anticipated yield for 145 regions can be found in the Supporting Information.

3.2. Impact on Prosumer Viability

The impact of the yield discrepancy on the yield of average systems in different regions presented in the previous subsection leads to the question how prosumer viability is affected. This subsection presents differences in solar PV capacity, stationary battery capacity, and ATCE of residential PV prosumer households in comparison.

3.2.1. Installed Solar PV Capacity

Presumable, less yield for rooftop PV systems will lead to higher demand for solar PV capacity of prosumer households. However, this question is more complex as the optimized system structure of prosumers depends on several factors more. **Figure 5** shows the difference in solar PV capacity of residential PV prosumer households if the yield losses are applied.

On the contrary to the presumption that less yield automatically must lead to higher solar PV capacities, the results show that in many regions less solar PV capacity is installed. Interestingly, in more regions, less solar PV capacity is more beneficial than no solar PV capacity at all (–100% change) already in 2020, indicating that the cost advantages of solar PV compared to grid supply of electricity is already favorable in many regions. However, a higher solar PV capacity is only installed in a few regions, mainly limited to South America, SSA, and Southeast Asia. This picture already changes in 2030, where many regions are already close to substitute 18% annual yield loss with up to 20% higher installed solar PV capacities. Some regions would not yet have solar PV capacities installed in 2020, but would have in 2030, either reduce the capacity in 2030 or avoid installation at all due to the yield losses. This effect is mostly evident in Eurasia. By 2040, negative changes get relatively rare. By 2050, almost all sunbelt regions substitute the yield losses with higher installed solar PV capacities, showing the very favorable economics of solar PV by mid-century. Nordic countries, on the contrary,

Figure 4. Anticipated yield expressed as FLH for residential rooftop PV systems (top left), commercial rooftop PV systems (top right), and industrial rooftop PV systems (bottom).

are not able to substitute the yield losses with higher solar PV capacities in an economically beneficial way, which can be seen by small negative changes in northern Europe and central Eurasia. In general, the cost reduction of solar PV in the future by 2050 is promising enough that most regions can balance lower yield compared to optimal systems with more installed capacity. A prerequisite would be the available rooftop area. Numeric differences in installed solar PV capacity for all regions and years can be found in the Supporting Information.

3.2.2. Installed Stationary Battery Capacity

In the previous study by Keiner et al.^[10] batteries have been identified to be the most flexible technology in terms of reacting to the availability of the grid connection. As can be seen in **Figure 6**, batteries also react in a very nonuniform way to the lower availability of rooftop solar PV yield.

In 2020, no change in stationary battery capacities is evident due to the fact that in the chosen scenario, batteries are mainly installed from 2025 onwards (cf. Keiner et al.^[10]). In 2030, many regions in the sunbelt increase their battery capacity together with solar PV capacity. Only a few regions in central Eurasia and Northeast Asia reduce the stationary battery capacity. For most regions, however, it seems that the reduced yield and consequently in general higher solar PV capacities (cf. **Figure 5**) rather leads to slightly increased battery capacities as well. In 2040, the situation is not very different from 2030 with a mix

of increased stationary battery capacity mostly in South America, SSA, Eurasia, and Southeast Asia, while in North America and Northeast Asia battery capacities are slightly reduced. By 2050, the change in stationary battery capacity is more homogeneous with a clear tendency to reduce battery capacities in North America, Europe, and Eurasia, whereas battery capacities stay more or less the same compared to no yield reduction or are slightly increased in the rest of the world. The relative change in stationary battery capacity is not as strong as for solar PV capacity in 2020 and 2050; however, in the time steps in between, namely 2030 and 2040, the optimized battery capacity reacts more strongly to the reduced yield. Numeric differences in installed stationary battery capacity for all regions and years can be found in the Supporting Information.

3.2.3. Annualized Total Cost of Energy

The objective of the optimization of the PV prosumer system is the ATCE. **Figure 7** shows the changes in ATCE for the residential PV prosumer system if yield losses are applied compared to the optimal system.

Contrary to the results presented up to now, the change in ATCE is rather homogeneous over the globe. In 2020, a few regions show a small change in ATCE. The reason is that, in 2020, the main supply via a rooftop PV system is not yet that pronounced, and for many regions a supply of electricity via the electricity grid is more beneficial. Nevertheless, many regions already

Figure 5. Difference in installed solar PV capacity for residential PV prosumer systems if yield losses are applied compared to an assumption of optimal yield profiles. A positive change indicates that that with losses applied, the installed solar PV capacity by the model is higher than without yield losses. Shown are the results for 2020 (top left), 2030 (top right), 2040 (bottom left), and 2050 (bottom right). No change (0%) might not only indicate no change in least-cost solar PV capacity but also that regions without solar PV capacity as least-cost option might not change their status of not having solar PV as part of their least-cost solution.

have the PV system as part of a least-cost solution. With the increasing importance of rooftop PV systems, the share of PV-supplied electricity grows as self-consumption becomes more favorable. Consequently, the ATCE raises in most regions by 2030 compared to an optimal solar PV yield. Only in Eurasia is this change not yet that evident as this is the region with the least strong development of rooftop PV system with a major increase post 2040. In 2040, the ATCEs of most of the regions are up to 20% higher than if the rooftop PV system would have an optimal yield. The same is the case in 2050. In the northern parts of North America, northern Europe, and Eurasia, the ATCEs increase by up to $\approx 10\%$ compared to the optimal yield. Conversely, in basically all other regions of the world, the ATCE increases by up to 21% and a global average of $\approx 16\%$. Though solar PV capacities and stationary battery capacities react very inhomogeneously to the lower yield situation, the cost almost linearly increases with the lower yield. If the optimized system solution includes less solar PV capacity, more electricity has to be drawn from the grid. If the solar PV system is already beyond grid parity, the lower availability of solar PV electricity is counterbalanced with an increased system design. Therefore, in technoeconomic modeling of energy systems, it is most important to make a dedicated modeling of solar PV prosumers with accordingly adapted yield profiles. Numeric differences in ATCE for all regions and years can be found in the Supporting Information.

4. Discussion

This study estimates the yield loss for residential rooftop solar PV systems to 18% annually, 7% annually for commercial systems, and 4% for industrial systems. A comparison of these values with other results in literature is not possible due to the lacking availability of comparable studies. This absence of literature rather comes as a surprise since rooftop solar PV and solar PV prosumers are usually assigned a significant role in the energy transition with its own broad field of research.^[61] Distributed solar PV power plants will support the energy transition on many levels, from using distributed inverters for frequency support and system recovery,^[62] via having a major share in electricity supply,^[5] to a decreased aging of transformers if electric vehicles are charged at home via solar PV plants instead of the grid.^[63] As shown in the literature review in Section 1, only very few energy system models include a differentiated solar PV prosumer sub-model or rooftop PV which, in the light of the “multi-talent” distributed solar PV, seems to be a major shortcoming in energy system research. The two leading reports on global energy transition, the World Energy Outlook of the IEA currently available in the 2023 version^[64] and the assessment report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change, latest available for the 6th assessment cycle,^[65] do not differentially mention the important role of distributed

Figure 6. Difference in installed stationary battery capacity for residential PV prosumer systems if yield losses are applied compared to an assumption of optimal yield profiles. A positive change indicates that with losses applied, the installed stationary battery capacity by the model is higher than without yield losses. Shown are the results for 2020 (top left), 2030 (top right), 2040 (bottom left), and 2050 (bottom right). No change (0%) might not only indicate no change in least-cost stationary battery capacity but also that regions without battery capacity as least-cost option might not change their status of not having a battery as part of their least-cost solution.

solar PV, rooftop solar PV, or solar PV prosumers, or simply include it generally in solar PV.

Based on the chosen assumptions, however, results for rooftop solar PV in energy systems might differ significantly when looking at extreme cases. While Bogdanov et al.^[5] find a high share of rooftop solar PV electricity generation of about 14.3 PWh of a total 104.3 PWh from solar PV in 2050 for a global transition toward 100% renewable energy in all energy sectors, the results of Gernaat et al.^[66] suggest ≈ 2.8 PWh in a total of ≈ 5.7 PWh electricity from solar PV by 2050 for the shared socio-economic pathway 2 (SSP2), which represents a “middle-of-the-road” world, following historical developments in social, economic, and technological trends.^[67] The SSP2 marker scenario, however, already suggests a total of ≈ 72 PWh electricity from solar PV by 2050. As mentioned in the introduction, the global rooftop solar PV market has been booming for several years. Gernaat et al.^[66] may serve as a negative example of misinterpreting the future role of solar PV in general and rooftop solar PV in particular, studies such as Bogdanov et al.^[5] will profit from the results in this study to refine their assumptions about rooftop solar PV. A showcase study in terms of consideration of rooftop PV may be Rahdan et al.^[25] who did a dedicated optimization on distribution grid level including rooftop PV, electric vehicles, etc. Future comparable studies will show if the yield reduction for rooftop solar PV as identified in the present article

will hinder the prospects of rooftop solar PV and prosumers, or the low-cost electricity option powered by the sun is more resilient to such changes due to a comfortable price buffer.

Yield profiles for rooftop solar PV are hard to obtain for global energy system modeling since, the yield of rooftop solar PV is different for each PV system. Therefore, the method presented in this study to obtain a general loss factor helps to identify rooftop solar PV profiles if ground-mounted yield profiles are available. Large-scale ground-mounted solar PV power plant profiles are easier to simulate as the yield calculation can be more simplified. Global simulations that rely on general data from satellites rather than specific on-site measurements depend on a simple, easy to use, and equation-based yield model for power plants, such as applied by Breyer and Schmidt,^[56] in contrast to detailed electric models of solar PV modules as for example presented by Cuce et al.^[68] These two studies shall act as examples for the wide variety of different modeling approaches available in literature. Fixed tilted utility-scale power plants may show yield losses due to mutual shading in the morning and evening hours. These losses, however, may not come as a disadvantage for the presented approach in this study since shading from housing structures and other obstacles usually affects the yield in the mornings and evenings on rooftops as well. Larger rooftop solar PV systems on commercial and industrial roofs are also often mounted and approximate with growing size the yield

Figure 7. Difference in ATCE for residential PV prosumer systems if yield losses are applied compared to an assumption of optimal yield profiles. A positive change indicates that with losses applied, the ATCE of the system are higher than without yield losses. Shown are the results for 2020 (top left), 2030 (top right), 2040 (bottom left), and 2050 (bottom right). No change (0%) might not only indicate no change in ATCE with the PV system but also that regions that did not install a PV system and relied fully on-grid supply do not change their 100% grid reliance.

and loss characteristics of ground-mounted power plants. This claim also has to be understood as an estimation, as actual shading from obstacles is again case- and roof-specific.^[37]

Depending on the definition, curtailment may be counted for as yield loss, too. High solar PV concentration in low voltage distribution grids may cause issues^[69] and regulatory measures may be in order to overcome such challenges.^[70] However, especially in densely populated urban areas the electricity demand may exceed the production from local solar PV.^[71] Additional deployment of storage such as batteries and flexibility options, in particular smart charging of electric vehicles and vehicle-to-grid^[72] may reduce the risk for curtailment. Seasonal storage for rooftop solar PV prosumers may not be economically beneficial^[10] and better be solved on a community-level.^[73]

This study has been carried out with currently available data on the loss effects of different system levels, which are rather limited. However, in case the availability of respective data improves, this study may have to be revised and adopted to new findings. One example is the use of microinverters for rooftop solar PV modules. Currently, no substantial market penetration can be identified from literature, nor for an outlook on the foreseeable future. However, if the techno-economics of the respective technology improves and becomes economically more attractive compared to conventional inverters, then the loss effects on system levels will have to be adapted. Long-term yield

disparities have to be checked including degradation effects of rooftop solar PV systems versus ground-mounted systems.

5. Conclusions

Understanding the yield prospects of rooftop solar PV power plants is necessary to allow for the rightful accounting of yield losses in energy system transition modeling with a differentiated consideration of solar PV prosumers. Usually, dedicated rooftop solar PV profiles are not available. This article presented the literature and method to estimate the yield losses of residential, commercial, and industrial rooftop solar PV systems in comparison to optimal yield represented by utility-scale ground-mounted solar PV power plants on three different levels: environmental level, cell and module level, and system level. The assessment indicated about 18% annual loss for average real-world residential systems compared to optimally simulated systems. This impact was estimated to be 7% for commercial-sized systems and to 4% for big-scale industrial rooftop PV systems.

The viability of residential solar PV prosumer systems with the reduced, that is, anticipated, yield has been assessed by comparing the total annualized cost of energy, including electricity demand, heat demand, and one-battery electric vehicle, in an on-grid case scenario for 145 regions globally. The results

indicate a nonuniform change in installed solar PV capacity and stationary battery capacity, due to individual parameter combinations and grid electricity cost for each region. For most regions, the missing yield of the solar photovoltaic system is counter-balanced with higher solar PV capacity by 2050 of up to 20%. The change in installed stationary battery capacity is similar; however, the change is not as significant as for the solar PV capacity. The annualized total cost of energy of the prosumer systems increases in all regions by 2050, as the cost-optimized average households are all equipped with a solar PV system by mid-century. On global average, an 18% yield reduction leads to about 16% higher system cost by 2050.

This study provided a novel view of the loss effect of rooftop solar PV systems compared to ground-mounted solar PV systems. The results indicate the significance of the necessity to include differentiated rooftop solar PV options in energy transition models, or solar PV prosumer sub-models in the best case, with a respective consideration of the yield losses. The results aim to improve the quality and detail of research of future energy system transition studies with a better consideration of one of the main pillars of the energy transition, which are distributed renewable energy sources such as rooftop solar PV.

Supporting Information

Supporting Information is available from the Wiley Online Library or from the author.

Acknowledgements

The authors gratefully acknowledge the public financing of European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programmed under grant agreement No. 953016 (SERENDI-PV), which partly funded this research. D.K. would like to thank the Jenny and Antti Wihuri Foundation for the valuable grant. The authors would like to thank Gabriel Lopez for proofreading.

Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Author Contributions

Dominik Keiner: Conceptualization (equal); Data curation (lead); Methodology (equal); Resources (lead); Validation (equal); Visualization (lead); Writing—original draft (lead). **Dmitrii Bogdanov:** Validation (equal); Writing—review and editing (supporting). **Stefan Krauter:** Validation (supporting). **Christian Breyer:** Conceptualization (equal); Methodology (equal); Supervision (lead); Validation (equal); Writing—review and editing (lead).

Data Availability Statement

Data sharing is not applicable to this article as no new data were created or analyzed in this study.

Keywords

battery, distributed, photovoltaics, prosumer, rooftop

Received: June 13, 2024
Revised: October 8, 2024
Published online: October 22, 2024

- [1] International Energy Agency (IEA), *World Energy Outlook 2020*, Paris **2020**, <https://www.iea.org/reports/world-energy-outlook-2020>.
- [2] International Renewable Energy Agency (IRENA), *Smart Electrification With Renewables: Driving the Transformation of Energy Services*, Abu Dhabi **2022**, https://www.irena.org/-/media/Files/IRENA/Agency/Publication/2022/Feb/IRENA_Smart-Electrification_Renewables_2022.pdf?prev=f4add985f6284a7cb811977c65b281b1.
- [3] S. Joshi, S. Mittal, P. Holloway, P. R. Shukla, B. Ó. Gallachóir, J. Glynn, *Nat. Commun.* **2021**, *12*, 5738.
- [4] International Energy Agency Photovoltaic Systems Programme (IEA-PVPS), *Trends in Photovoltaic Applications 2023*, Paris **2023**, https://iea-pvps.org/trends_reports/trends-2023/.
- [5] D. Bogdanov, M. Ram, A. Aghahosseini, A. Gulagi, A. S. Oyewo, M. Child, U. Caldera, K. Sadovskaia, J. Farfan, L. S. N. S. Barbosa, M. Fasih, S. Khalili, T. Traber, C. Breyer, *Energy* **2021**, *227*, 120467.
- [6] M. Z. Jacobson, M. A. Delucchi, M. A. Cameron, B. V. Mathiesen, *Renewable Energy* **2018**, *123*, 236.
- [7] International Energy Agency Photovoltaic Systems Programme (IEA-PVPS), *Snapshot of Global PV Markets 2023*, Paris **2023**, <https://iea-pvps.org/snapshot-reports/snapshot-2023/>.
- [8] International Energy Agency - Renewable Energy Technology Deployment (IEA-RETD), *Residential Prosumers - Drivers And Policy Options (RE-Prosumers)*, Paris **2014**, https://www.researchgate.net/publication/323663159_Residential_prosumers_-_Drivers_and_policy_options_RE-PROSUMERS.
- [9] D. Keiner, M. Ram, L. S. N. S. Barbosa, D. Bogdanov, C. Breyer, *Sol. Energy* **2019**, *185*, 406.
- [10] D. Keiner, C. Thoma, D. Bogdanov, C. Breyer, *Appl. Energy* **2023**, *340*, 121009.
- [11] K. Kotilainen, in *Affordable and Clean Energy* (Eds: W. Leal Filho, A. M. Azul, L. Brandli, P. G. Özuyar, T. Wall), Springer, Cham **2020**, pp. 1–14.
- [12] J. M. Wittmayer, I. Campos, F. Avelino, D. Brown, B. Doračić, M. Fraaije, S. Gährs, A. Hinsch, S. Assalini, T. Becker, E. Marín-González, L. Holstenkamp, R. , N. Duić, S. Oxenaar, T. Pukšec, *Energy Res. Soc. Sci.* **2022**, *86*, 102425.
- [13] M. Child, D. Bogdanov, A. Aghahosseini, C. Breyer, *Futures* **2020**, *124*, 102644.
- [14] A. B. Awan, M. Alghassab, M. Zubair, A. R. Bhatti, M. Uzair, G. Abbas, *Energies* **2020**, *13*, 3639.
- [15] N. Bansal, S. P. Jaiswal, G. Singh, *Sustainable Energy Technol. Assess.* **2021**, *47*, 101526.
- [16] S. Khalili, C. Breyer, *IEEE Access* **2022**, *10*, 125792.
- [17] H. Lund, J. Z. Thellufsen, P. A. Østergaard, P. Sorknæs, I. R. Skov, B. V. Mathiesen, *Smart Energy* **2021**, *1*, 100007.
- [18] R. Loulou, G. Goldstein, A. Kanudia, A. Lettila, U. Remme, *Documentation for the TIMES Model*, **2016**. https://iea-etsap.org/docs/Documentation_for_the_TIMES_Model-Part-I-July-2016.pdf.
- [19] European Commission - Joint Research Centre - Institute for Energy and Transport, *The JRC-EU-TIMES Model: Assessing the Long Term Role of the SET Plan Energy Technologies*, Publications Office, Luxembourg **2013**. <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2790/97596> (accessed: May, 2024).
- [20] F. Gardumi, A. Shivakumar, R. Morrison, C. Taliotis, O. Broad, A. Beltramo, V. Sridharan, M. Howells, J. Hörsch, T. Niet, Y. Almulla, E. Ramos, T. Burandt, G. P. Balderrama, G. N. Pinto De Moura, E. Zepeda, T. Alfstad, *Energy Strategy Rev.* **2018**, *20*, 209.
- [21] T. Niet, A. Shivakumar, F. Gardumi, W. Usher, E. Williams, M. Howells, *Energy Strategy Rev.* **2021**, *35*, 100650.

- [22] K. Löffler, K. Hainsch, T. Burandt, P.-Y. Oei, C. Kemfert, C. von Hirschhausen, *Energies* **2017**, *10*, 1468.
- [23] M. Z. Jacobson, M. A. Delucchi, M. A. Cameron, S. J. Coughlin, C. A. Hay, I. P. Manogaran, Y. Shu, A.-K. Von Krauland, *One Earth* **2019**, *1*, 449.
- [24] F. Neumann, E. Zeyen, M. Victoria, T. Brown, *Joule* **2023**, *7*, 1793.
- [25] P. Rahdan, E. Zeyen, C. Gallego-Castillo, M. Victoria, *Appl. Energy* **2024**, *360*, 122721.
- [26] W. J. Cole, D. Greer, P. Denholm, A. W. Frazier, S. Machen, T. Mai, N. Vincent, S. F. Baldwin, *Joule* **2021**, *5*, 1732.
- [27] K. Löffler, T. Burandt, K. Hainsch, P.-Y. Oei, F. Seehaus, F. Wejda, *Energy* **2022**, *239*, 121901.
- [28] T. Weber, A. Blakers, D. Firnando Silalahi, K. Catchpole, A. Nadolny, *Energy Convers. Manage.* **2024**, *308*, 118354.
- [29] J. Gea-Bermúdez, I. G. Jensen, M. Münster, M. Koivisto, J. G. Kirkerud, Y. Chen, H. Ravn, *Appl. Energy* **2021**, *289*, 116685.
- [30] G. Luderer, S. Madeddu, L. Merfort, F. Ueckerdt, M. Pehl, R. Pietzcker, M. Rottoli, F. Schreyer, N. Bauer, L. Baumstark, C. Bertram, A. Dirnaichner, F. Humpenöder, A. Levesque, A. Popp, R. Rodrigues, J. Streffer, E. Kriegler, *Nat. Energy* **2022**, *7*, 32.
- [31] H. C. Gils, H. Gardian, J. Schmutz, *Renewable Energy* **2021**, *180*, 140.
- [32] S. Teske, editor, in *Achieving the Paris Climate Agreement Goals*, Springer International Publishing, Cham **2019**.
- [33] International Energy Agency Photovoltaic Systems Programme (IEA-PVPS), *Uncertainties in PV System Yield Predictions and Assessments*, Paris **2018**, <https://iea-pvps.org/key-topics/uncertainties-in-pv-system-yield-predictions-and-assessments/>.
- [34] International Energy Agency Photovoltaic Systems Programme (IEA-PVPS), *Uncertainty in Yield Assessments and PV LCOE*, Paris **2020**, <https://iea-pvps.org/key-topics/uncertainties-yield-assessments/>.
- [35] International Energy Agency Photovoltaic Systems Programme (IEA-PVPS), *Performance of New Photovoltaic System Designs*, Paris **2021**, <https://iea-pvps.org/key-topics/performance-of-new-photovoltaic-system-designs/>.
- [36] S. Killinger, D. Lingfors, Y.-M. Saint-Drenan, P. Moraitis, W. van Sark, J. Taylor, N. A. Engerer, J. M. Bright, *Sol. Energy* **2018**, *173*, 1087.
- [37] G. Trzmiel, D. Gluchy, D. Kurz, *Renewable Energy* **2020**, *153*, 480.
- [38] U. Berardi, J. Graham, *Sustainable Cities Soc.* **2020**, *62*, 102402.
- [39] G. Y. Yun, M. McEvoy, K. Steemers, *Sol. Energy* **2007**, *81*, 383.
- [40] M. J. Ritzen, Z. A. E. P. Vroon, R. Rovers, A. Lupíšek, C. P. W. Geurts, *Sol. Energy* **2017**, *155*, 304.
- [41] G. Osma-Pinto, G. Ordóñez-Plata, *Sol. Energy* **2019**, *185*, 112.
- [42] R. Bründlinger, B. Bletterie, M. Milde, H. Oldenkamp, in *21st Eur. Photovoltaic Sol. Energy Conf.*, Dresden **2006**, pp. 2157–2160.
- [43] S. Kouro, J. I. Leon, D. Vinnikov, L. G. Franquelo, *IEEE Indus. Electron. Mag.* **2015**, *9*, 47.
- [44] D. Dong, M. S. Agamy, M. Harfman-Todorovic, X. Liu, L. Garces, R. Zhou, P. Cioffi, *IEEE Trans. Indus. Appl.* **2018**, *54*, 469.
- [45] A. Mohd, in *26th Eur. Photovoltaic Sol. Energy Conf. Exhib.*, WIP, Hamburg **2011**, pp. 3739–3744.
- [46] M. Gostein, B. Littmann, J. R. Caron, L. Dunn, in *2013 IEEE 39th Photovoltaic Special. Conf. (PVSC)*, IEEE, Tampa **2013**, pp. 3004–3009.
- [47] T. Townsend, P. Hutchinson, in *Proc. Sol. Conf.*, American Solar Energy Society, Madison **2000**, pp. 417–422.
- [48] R. J. Mustafa, M. R. Gormaa, M. Al-Dhaifallah, H. Rezk, *Sustainability* **2020**, *12*, 608.
- [49] A. M. Nobre, S. Karthik, H. Liu, D. Yang, F. R. Martins, E. B. Pereira, R. Rütger, T. Reindl, I. M. Peters, *Renewable Energy* **2016**, *89*, 389.
- [50] K. Hasan, S. B. Yousuf, M. S. H. K. Tushar, B. K. Das, P. Das, *Energy Sci. Eng.* **2022**, *10*, 656.
- [51] International Energy Agency Photovoltaic Systems Programme (IEA-PVPS), *Assessment of Performance Loss Rate of PV Power Systems*, Paris **2021**, <https://iea-pvps.org/key-topics/assessment-of-performance-loss-rate-of-pv-power-systems/>.
- [52] D. C. Jordan, S. R. Kurtz, K. VanSant, J. Newmiller, *Prog. Photovoltaics* **2016**, *24*, 978.
- [53] S. Herceg, I. Kaaya, J. Ascencio-Vásquez, M. Fischer, K.-A. Weiß, L. Schebek, *Sustainability* **2022**, *14*, 5843.
- [54] I. Kaaya, J. Ascencio-Vásquez, K.-A. Weiss, M. Topič, *Sol. Energy* **2021**, *218*, 354.
- [55] D. Bogdanov, C. Breyer, *Energy Convers. Manage.* **2016**, *112*, 176.
- [56] C. Breyer, J. Schmid, in *25th Eur. Photovoltaic Sol. Energy Conf. Exhib./5th World Conf. Photovoltaic Energy Convers.*, WIP, Valencia **2010**, pp. 4715–4721.
- [57] P. Stackhouse, C. Whitlock, *Surface Meteorology and Solar Energy (SSE) Release 6.0*, NASA SSE 6.0, https://searchworks.stanford.edu/catalog?q=%2522NASA%2bLangley%2bAtmospheric%2bSciences%2bData%2bCenter%2522%26search_field=search_author,Langley **2008**.
- [58] P. Stackhouse, C. Whitlock, *Surface Meteorology and Solar Energy (SSE) Release 6.0 Methodology*, NASA SSE 6.0, <https://power.larc.nasa.gov/docs/methodology/>, Langley **2009**.
- [59] D. Stetter, *Dissertation*, Faculty of Energy-, Process- and Bio-engineering, University of Stuttgart **2014**.
- [60] S. Afanasyeva, D. Bogdanov, C. Breyer, *Sol. Energy* **2018**, *173*, 173.
- [61] Y. Shen, L. Ji, Y. Xie, G. Huang, X. Li, L. Huang, *Energy Build.* **2021**, *251*, 111333.
- [62] H. Dehghanifaki, G. Konstantinou, J. Fletcher, L. Callegaro, G. Farivar, J. Pou, *IEEE Trans. Power Electron.* **2022**, *37*, 4742.
- [63] M. K. Gray, W. G. Morsi, *Electric Power Syst. Res.* **2017**, *143*, 563.
- [64] International Energy Agency (IEA), *World Energy Outlook 2023*, Paris **2023**, <https://origin.iea.org/reports/world-energy-outlook-2023>.
- [65] Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC), *Climate Change 2023: Synthesis Report. Contribution of Working Groups I, II and III to the Sixth Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change*, Geneva **2023**.
- [66] D. E. H. J. Gernaat, H.-S. de Boer, L. C. Dammeier, D. P. van Vuuren, *Appl. Energy* **2020**, *279*, 115705.
- [67] O. Fricko, P. Havlik, J. Rogelj, Z. Klimont, M. Gusti, N. Johnson, P. Kolp, M. Strubegger, H. Valin, M. Amann, T. Ermolieva, N. Forsell, M. Herrero, C. Heyes, G. Kindermann, V. Krey, D. L. McCollum, M. Obersteiner, S. Pachauri, S. Rao, E. Schmid, W. Schoepp, K. Riahi, *Glob. Environ. Change* **2017**, *42*, 251.
- [68] E. Cuce, P. M. Cuce, I. H. Karakas, T. Bali, *Energy Convers. Manage.* **2017**, *146*, 205.
- [69] T. Aziz, N. Ketjoy, *IEEE Access* **2017**, *5*, 16784.
- [70] G. Tévar, A. Gómez-Expósito, A. Arcos-Vargas, M. Rodríguez-Montañés, *Int. J. Electr. Power Energy Syst.* **2019**, *106*, 68.
- [71] M. Ram, A. Gulagi, A. Aghahosseini, D. Bogdanov, C. Breyer, *Renewable Energy* **2022**, *195*, 578.
- [72] D. Bogdanov, C. Breyer, *Energy* **2024**, *301*, 131635.
- [73] P. Grunow, *Energies* **2022**, *15*, 2820.
- [74] I. H. Rowlands, B. P. Kemery, I. Beausoleil-Morrison, *Energy Policy* **2011**, *39*, 1397.
- [75] H. Byrd, *The Solar Potential of Auckland*, The University of Auckland, Auckland **2012**.
- [76] Y. S. Khoo, A. Nobre, R. Malhotra, D. Yang, R. Ruther, T. Reindl, A. G. Aberle, *IEEE J. Photovoltaics* **2014**, *4*, 647.
- [77] M. Hartner, A. Ortner, A. Hiesl, R. Haas, *Appl. Energy* **2015**, *160*, 94.
- [78] B. Matthiss, D. Stellbogen, M. Eberspächer, J. Binder, in *31st Eur. Photovoltaic Sol. Energy Conf. Exhib.*, WIP, Hamburg **2015**, pp. 2311–2314.
- [79] S. Kichou, N. Skandalos, P. Wolf, *J. Phys.: Conf. Ser.* **2019**, *1343*, 012093.
- [80] M. Oh, H.-D. Park, *Energies* **2019**, *12*, 3262.
- [81] C. Yu, Y. Khoo, J. Chai, S. Han, J. Yao, *Sustainability* **2019**, *11*, 2016.